

Inner Speech and the Paradox of Emotional Dysregulation: Neuromodulatory Structures, Physiological Coordination and the Evolutionary Impact of Internal Language on the Organism's Imbalance

João Carlos Orquiza¹

Abstract

Internal speech, a human ability based on the expression of the *FOXP2* gene, was initially an advantageous evolutionary adaptation, offering the organism mechanisms of planning, cooperation and protection. However, over the course of social development and the complexification of human interactions, internal speech has become a paradoxical source of threat, activating the body's defense system and imposing a constant physiological load that affects health and interpersonal relationships. This article explores, in an integrated way, the function of neuromodulators, the role of blood circulation, motor behavior, internal motor speech and the areas structured for defense, proposing a new understanding of emotion as a protective structure. Finally, we discuss the paradox generated by internal speech as it reconfigures itself from a defense tool to a continuous threat mechanism, generating fundamental implications for health and social cohesion.

Keywords: Internal speech, FOXP2 gene, Neuromodulators, Motor behavior, Blood circulation, Physiological coordination, Emotion as a defense structure, Emotion regulation, Emotional dysregulation, Internal speech paradox, Evolutionary impact of internal language, Mental health, Resilience of the organism, Social cohesion

1. "Psychology Undergraduate, Universidade Positivo. Londrina/PR/Brazil. ORCID:
<https://orcid.org/0000-0001-9619-9939>. Email: joao.carlos56@cs.up.edu.br

INTRODUCTION

The ability to speak internally is an essential evolutionary milestone for *Homo sapiens*, providing a framework for thought, planning, and internal communication that enhances survival and social coordination (Bermúdez 2003). This ability, mediated by the *FOXP2* gene, is not merely symbolic or abstract; it involves a series of interconnected brain structures, activating networks of neuromodulators and triggering real physiological responses that ensure the protection of the organism (Vargha-Khadem et al. 2005). However, internal speech has evolved beyond its original purpose, generating a paradox where what should function as defense and integration has become a source of conflict and threat.

This article aims to deeply analyze the neuromodulatory bases associated with internal speech, its role as a motor process, the importance of blood circulation in the integration of the defense system, and the emerging paradox of internal speech in emotional regulation. Understanding these aspects can provide valuable insights into how self-speech influences the body's mental health and resilience.

METHODOLOGY

In this theoretical study, the author employed logical reasoning to explore and connect concepts related to internal speech and emotional regulation. Through a critical and reflective analysis, paradoxes and evolutionary implications were identified that had not been widely discussed in the literature. The integrative literature review served to support and validate

the theoretical propositions, ensuring that they were based on scientific evidence and recognized theories.

NEUROMODULATORY BASES AND INTERNAL SPEECH AS A MOTOR PROCESS

Neuromodulators, including dopamine, serotonin, norepinephrine, and acetylcholine, play crucial roles in modulating emotional state, organizing motor behavior, and regulating internal speech (Kringelbach and Berridge 2017). These neurotransmitters adjust the level of arousal, attention, and emotional response of the organism, promoting a protective system that reacts to internal and external stimuli with the aim of ensuring survival (Bear, Connors, and Paradiso 2016).

Internal speech is not an isolated or purely symbolic mental process, but an internal motor process that utilizes motor and language areas of the brain to simulate verbal communication, even without external expression (Alderson-Day and Fernyhough 2015). This process involves the same motor planning and organization networks as external speech, regulated by the basal ganglia, responsible for the automation of motor sequences (Alexander, DeLong and Strick 1986). This motor control integrated with internal speech demonstrates that verbalized thought is a coordinated action, influencing the activation of neuromodulatory networks and promoting specific physiological responses.

THE ROLE OF BLOOD CIRCULATION IN THE INTERCONNECTION OF THE DEFENSE SYSTEM

Blood circulation acts as an integrating link, allowing neuromodulators, oxygen, and glucose to be distributed instantaneously throughout the body (Silverthorn 2010). In situations of emotional alertness, blood flow is directed to critical areas, adjusting the state of cellular readiness and response (Lovallo 2016). Thus, emotion can be reinterpreted not as an isolated subjective experience, but as a physiological defense structure, regulating the organism in real time.

In addition, blood circulation allows the autonomic nervous system to adjust the body's defense response, promoting balance through the parasympathetic system or increasing alertness via the sympathetic system, as the situation demands (McCorry 2007). This continuous flow of resources demonstrates that emotion is not just an abstract reaction, but a coordinated cellular response, essential for the integrity of the organism.

THE PARADOX OF INTERNAL SPEECH: A DEFENSE TOOL THAT TURNS AGAINST THE ORGANISM

Internal speech, since the emergence of the *FOXP2* gene, has served as a protective mechanism, promoting planning, self-assessment, and adaptive responsiveness (Fisher and Scharff 2009). However, with the complexification of human interactions, internal speech began to be used to formulate and interpret threats, including internal judgments and criticisms (Morin 2011). By interpreting a negative internal word as a threat, the body activates the defense system, triggering a physiological response that

includes increased heart rate, cortisol release, and adjustments in the sympathetic nervous system (Sapolsky 2004).

This process creates a paradox: internal speech, which should promote defense and social integration, has become a source of wear, activating constant defense responses and imposing a chronic physiological load on the organism (Brinker, Campisi, and Gibbs 2013). The cycle of defensive activation repeats itself, generating prolonged states of alertness and impairing the balance and health of the organism, contributing to disorders such as anxiety and depression (Watkins 2008).

CONCLUSION

The integrated analysis of neuromodulators, blood circulation, motor areas and internal speech reveals that the body's defense system is deeply interconnected and coordinated, not just a reaction to external stimuli, but a continuous and adaptive response. Internal speech, although initially an advantageous evolutionary tool, has become a paradox: a favorable adaptation that, over time, has come to represent a source of internal threat (Hurlburt, Heavey, and Kelsey 2013). This paradox exposes internal speech as a mechanism that, when interacting with the defense system, can generate internal and social conflicts that impact health and cohesion among individuals.

This study proposes a new understanding of emotion and internal speech as integrated structures of defense and adaptation. Recognizing the paradoxical role of internal speech in emotion regulation is essential to develop strategies that redirect this process, reducing its negative impact and promoting a sustainable balance in the organism and social relationships

(Leary and Tate 2007). Therapeutic interventions that target cognitive restructuring and mindfulness may be effective in mitigating the deleterious effects of negative internal speech by restoring its original protective function (Segal, Williams, and Teasdale 2018).

REFERENCES

1. Alderson-Day, Ben, e Charles Fernyhough. "Inner Speech: Development, Cognitive Functions, Phenomenology, and Neurobiology." *Psychological Bulletin* 141.5 (2015): 931-965.
2. Alexander, George E., Mahlon R. DeLong, e Peter L. Strick. "Parallel Organization of Functionally Segregated Circuits Linking Basal Ganglia and Cortex." *Annual Review of Neuroscience* 9 (1986): 357-381.
3. Bear, Mark F., Barry W. Connors, and Michael A. Paradiso. *Neurosciences: Unraveling the Nervous System*. 4th ed., Artmed, 2017.
4. Bermúdez, José Luis. *Thinking without Words*. Oxford University Press, 2003.
5. Brinker, Jay K., Nicholas M. Campisi, e Lisa Gibbs. "Rumination, Mood and Cognitive Performance." *Psychology* 4.3 (2013): 224-231.
6. Fisher, Simon E., e Constance Scharff. "FOXP2 as a Molecular Window into Speech and Language." *Trends in Genetics* 25.4 (2009): 166-177.
7. Hurlburt, Russell T., Christopher L. Heavey, e Jason M. Kelsey. "Toward a Phenomenology of Inner Speaking." *Consciousness and Cognition* 22.4 (2013): 1477-1494.

8. Kringelbach, Morten L., e Kent C. Berridge. "The Affective Core of Emotion: Linking Pleasure, Subjective Well-Being, and Optimal Metastability in the Brain." *Emotion Review* 9.3 (2017): 191-199.
9. Leary, Mark R., e Emily B. Tate. "The Self as a Source of Suffering." *Self and Identity* 6.4 (2007): 325-333.
10. Lovallo, William R. *Stress and Health: Biological and Psychological Interactions*. 3^a ed., Sage Publications, 2016.
11. McCorry, Laurie K. "Physiology of the Autonomic Nervous System." *American Journal of Pharmaceutical Education* 71.4 (2007): 78.
12. Morin, Alain. "Self-Awareness Part 1: Definition, Measures, Effects, Functions, and Antecedents." *Social and Personality Psychology Compass* 5.10 (2011): 807-823.
13. Sapolsky, Robert M. *Why Zebras Don't Get Ulcers*. 3^a ed., Henry Holt and Company, 2004.
14. Segal, Zindel V., J. Mark G. Williams, e John D. Teasdale. *Mindfulness-Based Cognitive Therapy for Depression*. 2^a ed., Guilford Press, 2018.
15. Silverthorn, Dee Unglaub. *Human physiology: an integrated approach*. 6th ed., Artmed, 2013.
16. Vargha-Khadem, Faraneh, et al. "FOXP2 and the Neuroanatomy of Speech and Language." *Nature Reviews Neuroscience* 6.2 (2005): 131-138.
17. Watkins, Edward R. "Constructive and Unconstructive Repetitive Thought." *Psychological Bulletin* 134.2 (2008): 163-206.